

Automated Design Sustainability Evaluation Framework: A CAD-Integrated Tool for Real-Time Costing and LCA in Automotive Engineering

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Abstract

As the automotive industry faces increasingly rigorous environmental regulations and an approaching obligation for Digital Product Passports (DPPs), incorporating sustainability metrics into the early design phase has become a necessity. Traditionally, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and manufacturing cost estimation are performed during or after the design phase using specific methods and tools, resulting in costly iterations and delayed decision-making. This paper introduces a preliminary computational tool that combines 3D CAD and spreadsheet software via VBA integration. The framework automates the generation of an "Extended Bill of Materials" by extracting geometric and manufacturing data directly from CAD models. This tool's classification logic is a key innovation that intelligently processes CAD features to identify component categories, such as sheet metal, machined parts, or

plastic injections. This automated recognition allows the framework to implement specific algorithmic models for the preliminary estimation of production costs and environmental impact indicators. The gap between computer-aided design and sustainability analysis is partially bridged by the tool, enabling engineers to receive immediate feedback on the carbon footprint and recyclability of their designs during the early conceptual stage. Preliminary testing within automotive case studies shows a substantial decrease in lead times for technical estimation. Specifically, analysis time was reduced by at least 90%, with subsystems processed in under 10 minutes, a significant improvement over traditional manual calculations. This tool represents a pragmatic step toward "Circular Design" paradigms, supporting compliance with future legislative frameworks and fostering the transition toward a circular economy in transportation systems.

Keywords

Circular Design, Life Cycle Assessment, Cost Analysis, CAD, Digital Product Passport, Sustainability, Carbon Footprint

Introduction

The automotive industry is undergoing a major transformation due to increasingly severe environmental regulations and intensified demand to reduce lifecycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Regulatory initiatives, including the European Green Deal [1], which targets climate neutrality by 2050, are changing vehicle development requirements and forcing manufacturers and suppliers to include sustainability metrics into engineering processes. Compliance is shifting from a reporting function to a design-driven mandate that directly affects product

architecture, material selection, and manufacturing process planning. Automotive original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and their supply chains now prioritize transitioning from the linear "take-make-dispose" model to Circular Economy (CE) principles as a strategic objective [2]. Using Circular Design paradigms [3,4], CE frameworks increase resource efficiency, recyclability [5], and reduce lifecycle waste, while also supporting regulatory compliance and cost control [6]. Emerging legislation, such as the Digital Product Passport (DPP), will require comprehensive traceability of material content and environmental performance

at the component level [7]. In this context, recent research has demonstrated that data within the International Material Data System (IMDS) represents a useful and accessible source of data for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) experts in the automotive industry, effectively bridging the gap between mandatory material reporting and environmental impact assessment [8]. These requirements necessitate increased data transparency and availability throughout the product lifecycle. Manufacturers are therefore required to form digital information flows that integrate design, production and sustainability evaluation. From an engineering point of view, these regulatory developments add new requirements during early product development. It is acknowledged that a significant percentage of a product's final manufacturing cost and environmental impact is determined during the design phase [9]. Nevertheless, detailed LCA and cost analysis are predominantly performed in later development stages, typically as verification activities rather than as decision-support tools. This sequential workflow restricts engineering teams' capacity to assess regulatory compliance and sustainability performance while maintaining high design flexibility and relatively low modification costs [8]. Current industrial workflows reveal a gap between Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and sustainability platforms. Although numerous eco-design tools exist [10,11], most function as standalone systems and require manual data input and interpretation. This procedure can result in data inconsistencies, weakened traceability, and extended development lead times, thereby challenging rapid vehicle development cycles and regulatory inspection requirements. Remic et al. (2024) [12] conducted a comparative analysis of in-design sustainability assessment tools, evaluating LCA software such as SimaPro and integrated CAD solutions including SolidWorks Sustainability and Autodesk Fusion 360. The study recognized key challenges: inconsistencies in impact calculation, limited transparency in material databases, and strict energy modeling for manufacturing. These findings underscore the need for straightforward, configurable, and engineering-oriented sustainability frameworks. In addition to environmental performance, automotive product development must also address economic feasibility. Integrating cost analysis with LCA is fundamental to ensuring that design solutions meet regulatory environmental targets without resulting in unacceptable manufacturing costs or supply chain risks. While prior research has analyzed CAD-integrated LCA approaches [13], few methodologies offer automated feature recognition that translates geometric design data into manufacturing process classification without substantial manual input. Moreover, many existing commercial solutions operate as "black-box" systems, offering limited understanding into the main algorithms used for impact and cost estimation. This practice hinders the verification of environmental claims and restricts the customization required for specific automotive supply chains. Consequently, transparent and adaptable methodologies are essential for encouraging trust among design engineers and ensuring that sustainability metrics are correctly interpreted. This limitation impedes scalability and adoption in industrial engineering settings. The increasing complexity of regulatory frameworks, including circular

design directives and digital traceability mandates, will require engineering organizations to implement design tools that deliver sustainability and cost feedback directly during product modeling [14]. Such tools must ensure digital continuity, standardized data structures, and facilitate regulatory documentation generation while lowering additional engineering workload. To address these challenges, this study suggests a computational framework that connects a 3D CAD environment to Microsoft Excel via VBA (Visual Basic for Applications) automation. The system enables rapid estimation of environmental and cost impacts during component design. Unlike static or manual databases, the framework uses classification logic to generate an "extended" Bill of Materials (BOM), supporting both manufacturing planning and sustainability reporting. The system automatically extracts geometrical attributes from CAD models and assigns them to manufacturing process categories, such as sheet metal forming, injection molding, and machining. Parametric cost estimation methods [15] and environmental performance indicators are then applied to facilitate a fast design evaluation. This approach is aimed at improving engineering decision-making while advancing data traceability and compliance readiness. The advantage of this approach, compared to existing ones that operate as a "black box", limiting themselves to environmental impact and approximating energy mixes for broad macro-regions, relies on ensuring complete transparency and accuracy by relying on rigorous, localized data from commercial environmental databases that can be tailored to a specific geographic area. Furthermore, thanks to the dynamic nature of the Excel file generated, which contains dynamic and parameterized formulas, the tool allows users to modify database data without having to rerun the simulation.

Work Structure and Objectives

The objective of this study is to create a scalable workflow that enables automotive engineers to evaluate carbon footprint and manufacturing cost at the same time during the design process to help them in decision-making and to compile future DPPs. The structure of the paper is as follows. The Methods section details the automated framework and calculation methodologies, including their implementation. The Results section presents two preliminary automotive case studies focused on motorsport component development. The Discussion section assesses the applicability of the suggested methodology within an industrial context. The Conclusions and Recommendations sections summarize the key findings, strengths and limitations of the method, and suggests future directions for industrial implementation and regulatory integration.

Methods

This study presents a framework to bypass the drawbacks of existing automated sustainability and cost evaluation tools, building on the research framework described

in the previous chapter. The main objective of this work is to implement a Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) framework that allows for advanced interoperability between Microsoft Excel [16] and a three-dimensional CAD platform, specifically SolidWorks 2025 [17]. Automating the creation of the BOM and running algorithms for LCA analysis and preliminary production cost estimation are the two main goals of the suggested framework. Reducing costing lead times and offering early sustainability feedback during the conceptual design phase are two important industrial requirements that this methodology directly addresses. Recent studies support the efficiency of VBA-based automation in engineering design environments. For instance, Esanakula (2024) [18] demonstrated that integrating SolidWorks Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) with Knowledge-Based Engineering (KBE) approaches significantly improves the efficiency of engineering workflows. The study found that using structured decision-making algorithms reduced modeling time by 50% and significantly reduced human-induced errors related to repetitive design tasks. Consistent with these findings, the framework suggested in this research follows a sequential workflow that is structured and made up of three main operational phases:

- *Data Extraction.* Data acquisition is ensured by systematically retrieving geometric parameters and physical properties from the active CAD model via direct API interaction.
- *Data Processing.* Heuristic-based decision logic classifies extracted components into predefined manufacturing categories, such as raw materials, sheet metal components, and polymer-based parts. Then, using the unique characteristics of each component, production cost indicators and environmental impact metrics are calculated.
- *Data Reporting and Visualization.* The system automatically creates a multi-sheet, structured Excel report that includes component preview photos, graphical visualizations, and quantitative data summaries. The purpose of this reporting framework is to facilitate informed decision-making in the early phases of design evaluation and to help engineers construct a Digital Product Passport for the component.

A schematic representation of the framework's operation is shown in Figure 1, illustrating the workflow stages detailed in the subsequent sections. Although the present activity is based on VBA and SolidWorks integration, the workflow is applicable to most engineering CAD environments and can potentially be implemented using different scripting languages and software platforms.

Product CAD Analysis

The initial phase consists in analyzing a CAD assembly representing a vehicle subsystem. The system employs a recursive algorithm to traverse the CAD feature tree, extracting data regarding materials, mass properties, and

FIGURE 1 Framework methodology workflow.

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physical attributes for every active component to create the basis of the Bill of Materials. Detailed information regarding the script implementation and logic can be found in Table A1 in Appendix. Furthermore, it analyzes specific construction features to verify manufacturing classifications. The following component categories are recognized for manufacturing analysis:

- *Sheet Metal Components.* Identification is achieved by detecting specific sheet metal module features (e.g., *FlatPattern*) or by performing constant-thickness analysis. For these components, the system automatically calculates the dimensions of the flattened pattern, a critical data point for precise cost estimation for laser cutting.
- *Plastics and Additive Manufacturing.* Identification occurs via specific keyword searches within the material definition (e.g., "PLA", "ABS", "Resin") or by analyzing custom properties (e.g., "Technology: 3D Print"). Volume and mass are calculated for these parts, serving as essential parameters for estimating deposition or injection molding costs.
- *Standard Raw Materials.* All remaining components not falling into the above-mentioned categories (typically designed to be produced by subtractive manufacturing processes such as turning or milling) are analyzed based on the Bounding Box calculation (maximum Cartesian dimensions) and material density.

To maximize the clarity of the final report, the code integrates a module for automatic screenshot generation, providing a visual reference for each component. A “visual optimization” algorithm is executed to isolate, clean, standardize, and center the component view before dynamically importing it into the Excel cell. The comprehensive step-by-step procedure of this visualization algorithm is detailed in [Table A1](#) in Appendix.

The outcome of this phase is the transition from a CAD assembly file to a structured Excel spreadsheet comprising the extended BOM. This document details the mass, materials, and primary manufacturing processes for each component, making it ready for subsequent phases of cost analysis and environmental impact assessment.

Cost Analysis

The production cost analysis for internally manufactured, “make”, components (as opposed to commercial off-the-shelf, “buy”, components, which are assigned a fixed procurement cost) adopts specific cost functions differentiated by manufacturing technology:

- *Sheet Metal Formulation*. This employs a parametric model that accounts for the cutting path length, the number of bends, and the raw material cost per kilogram.
- *Additive Manufacturing Formulation*. The cost basis is derived from the specific cost of the filament or resin per unit weight, combined with an hourly machine rate applied to the total printing or injection cycle time.
- *Machining Formulation*. Calculations are based on the volume of the enclosing Bounding Box multiplied by the raw material cost per kilogram, thereby simulating the material waste associated with subtractive machining processes.
- *Welding Formulation*. The calculations are based on the size of the weld beads.

The corresponding equations are shown in [Table A2](#) in the Appendix; the costs model are based on literature [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25] and modified to adapt to the specific case study.

LCA Analysis

Regarding the environmental assessment, the system currently computes the impact utilizing the Carbon Footprint indicator (Global Warming Potential - GWP100), in accordance with the LCIA Environmental Footprint (EF) v3.1 methodology, the recommended one by European Union Commission [26]. The analysis follows a cradle-to-gate approach compatible with ISO 14040 standard [27]. Within the defined product system, the evaluation contains the environmental burdens associated with raw material acquisition and the manufacturing processes required to realize the final product.

The cumulative impact of the assembly design is quantified in kg CO_{2,eq}. This direct methodology enables immediate estimation of the environmental effects of specific design decisions, aligning with the principles of Circular Design. Data source can be a commercial database (e.g. Ecoinvent data), to be acquired separately, or a subset of it.

In addition to the cradle-to-gate LCA, the algorithm conducts a preliminary End-of-Life (EoL) analysis. The methodology is grounded in the ISO 22628 [28] standard (Road Vehicles) and also permits the integration of the UNIFE (European Rail Supply Industry) and ISO 21106 [29,30] (Railway applications) guidelines. Unlike the standard automotive approach, the ISO 21106 methodology incorporates process efficiency coefficients into the calculation of Recyclability (RR) and Recoverability (RRR) rates, thereby offering a more realistic assessment of industrial recycling capabilities [31]. The core of this analysis is the *CreateRecyclingSheet* procedure. Starting from manual calculation methods, the code instantaneously categorizes the vehicle’s mass distribution into standard ISO recyclability classes. Afterwards, the algorithm aggregates component masses into critical categories derived directly from the CAD model’s physical properties:

- Ferrous and Non-ferrous Metals.
- Thermoplastics and Elastomers.
- Electrical and Electronic Components.

While the ISO 22628 standard typically assigns theoretical recovery rates, the developed code can implement the conservative efficiency factors defined by ISO21106/UNIFE to reflect the industrial reality of Material Recovery Facilities (MRF); suitable examples are:

- *Ferrous Metals*. A coefficient of 0.98 is applied, reflecting the high efficiency of magnetic separation processes.
- *Elastomers*. A significantly reduced rate (0.1) is applied to simulate mechanical losses and contamination, as described in dismantling manuals.
- *Thermosets*. The rate is reduced to 0.05, as these materials are predominantly destined for energy recovery rather than material recycling.

Furthermore, the system models a realistic recycling scenario, considering a mix of *non-functional recycling* (representing often the worst-case or open-loop recycling) and *functional recycling* (representing the best-case or closed-loop recycling). In the latter scenario, materials are recovered to fulfill their original function without value degradation. Evaluating a mix of the two cases is essential for estimating a realistic potential environmental credit (avoided burden) recoverable at the end of life, while accounting for the impacts of the recycling processes themselves. These analyses are critical for the prospective integration of component data into the Digital Product Passport.

Output

The culmination of the analysis is the generation of a structured Excel file, organized into distinct worksheets:

- *Component Database.* An exhaustive inventory comprising all assembly components, accompanied by their corresponding visual thumbnails and full file directory paths.
- *Detailed Technical Sheets.* Dedicated worksheets for Sheet Metal, Plastics, and Raw Materials components, tabulating the extracted geometric dimensions and process-specific calculations.
- *Graphical Dashboards.* Two executive summary sheets (“Cost Overview” and “LCA Overview”) aggregate the cumulative data. The integration of dynamic charting provides an immediate visualization of impact distribution, identifying critical hotspots and thereby supporting data-driven decision-making.

The system includes a dedicated module for compiling suggestions for the Digital Product Passport, executed via the *CreateProductPassport* subroutine. This module extracts the computed environmental and cost data and inserts them directly into the SolidWorks file’s custom properties. This process establishes an intrinsic link between the 3D geometric model and its associated environmental metadata. The final output is a PDF report that effectively transforms raw design data into a standardized, comparable format ready for sequential utilization.

Case Studies

This work analyzes two distinct case studies, both focusing on assemblies related to a Formula SAE/Student competition vehicle. Beyond serving as exemplary automotive components, specifically within the motorsport domain with a strong emphasis on manufacturing phases, these cases address the evolving Formula Student regulations. The competition’s Cost and Manufacturing Event has recently incorporated the necessity to do an environmental impact analysis to compile the new CCBOM (Costed Carbonized Bill of Material) [32], calculated using the $CO_{2,eq}$ indicator, making the presented framework highly valuable for teams seeking a compliant analysis.

The *first case study* examines an assembly comprising the tubular chassis of the FR-25, the vehicle developed by the Firenze Race Team (FRT - University of Florence) [33] for the 2025 season, along with its associated welding jigs. The *second case study* focuses on the autonomous steering assembly. This system is of particular interest due to its critical components for environmental impact analysis; specifically, it uses an actuation motor with Permanent Magnets (PMs). These components are a primary focus of emerging legislation, such as the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) [34] and the future DPP. This choice arises because PMs often contain Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), such as Rare Earth Elements (REEs) (e.g., Neodymium), which differ

significantly in their environmental, economic, and social impacts [35,36]. Consequently, future regulations will require these materials to be explicitly declared in product datasheets to facilitate disassembly and maximize recycling potential [37].

FIGURE 2 First case study: tubular chassis with its associated welding jigs. Firenze Race Team, 2025 [33].

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FIGURE 3 Second case study: autonomous steering assembly. Firenze Race Team, 2025 [33].

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It is crucial to note that the practical application of the proposed algorithm relies on its integration with a comprehensive database. This database must encompass all necessary coefficients for both cost estimation and Life Cycle Assessment. For the environmental analysis presented in this work, the data utilized are sourced from Ecoinvent version 3.10.1 [38]. For the end-of-life analysis of the case studies, specific functional and non-functional recycling parameters were considered, trying to make the calculation of environmental credit as realistic as possible with respect to the context in which it is calculated.

Results

The analysis of the first case study, focusing on the chassis and its associated welding jigs, indicates a total cost of €

7741. The distribution of these costs is presented in [Figure 4](#). This case study is typically representative of welded steel structures: on this occasion, a FeNiCrMo alloy frequently used in vehicle welded frame applications.

Regarding the environmental impact, the calculated carbon footprint is 2154.3 kg CO_{2,eq}, with the breakdown shown in [Figure 5](#).

[Table 1](#) summarizes the Recyclability Rate (RR) and Recoverability Rate (RRR) factors, calculated in accordance with ISO 22628 and ISO 21106 methodologies.

Regarding the potential End-of-Life (EoL) scenario, it yields a possible environmental credit of approximately 402.8 kg CO_{2,eq}. A more detailed representation is visible in [Table A3](#) in Appendix, which represents a summary of the results shown to the tool user, who can use them to compile a future DPP regarding the carbon footprint, economic analysis and potential environmental credit during the EoL of the examined assembly.

FIGURE 4 Cost distribution, chassis case study.

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FIGURE 5 CO_{2,eq} distribution, chassis case study.

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TABLE 1 Recyclability and Recoverability indicators, chassis case study.

	ISO22628	ISO21106
RR	100 %	98.0 %
RRR	100 %	99.8 %

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FIGURE 6 Cost distribution, autonomous steering system case study.

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FIGURE 7 CO_{2,eq} distribution, autonomous steering system case study.

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The second case study, concerning the autonomous steering system, exhibits distinct results. The system is a complex assembly, which includes more than 400 components: mechanical parts (bearing, joint, shafts) and mechatronic units (motor, driver, transmission, display on the steering wheel, etc.) The total cost is circa € 3445, distributed as shown in [Figure 6](#).

The calculated carbon footprint stands at 575.3 kg CO_{2,eq}, distributed as represented in [Figure 7](#).

The RR and RRR factors, derived in accordance with ISO 22628 and ISO 21106 standards, are listed in [Table 2](#).

Under the examined EoL scenario, the potential environmental credit is 32.3 kg CO_{2,eq}. In the same way as was done for the first case, [Table A4](#) in Appendix shows the summary of the results for this second assembly, quickly demonstrating a complete analysis of the CAD model from the point of view of environmental impact and economic assessment.

TABLE 2 Recyclability and Recoverability indicators, autonomous steering system case study.

	ISO22628	ISO21106
RR	98.7 %	97.3 %
RRR	98.7 %	98.5 %

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Discussion

The implementation of the proposed computational framework within the two case studies demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating sustainability and cost parameters directly with the 3D CAD environment. By automating the transition from geometric modeling to an “extended bill of materials”, the tool partially addresses the “disconnection” between design and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) identified in the Introduction.

The results of the *first case study* (tubular chassis) highlight the significant impact of structural components. With an environmental impact of 2154.3 kg CO_{2,eq}, the chassis is a significant contributor to the vehicle's overall carbon footprint. Cost distribution (Figure 4) and carbon dioxide equivalent distribution (Figure 5) suggest that, while raw material extraction dominates the environmental load, production complexity (welding and mask preparation) plays a substantial role in economic valuation (€ 7741). To address the need for validation, the framework's estimations for the tubular chassis were compared against reference data from similar Formula Student projects. Economically, for example, welding process costs estimated by the VBA tool align with the manufacturing costs reported by Fuentes Martínez et al. [39], falling within the same order of magnitude despite justifiable variations due to different welding technologies (e.g., TIG vs. MIG). Environmentally, the calculated carbon footprint for the structural frame is conceptually comparable to the impacts reported by Ros et al. [40] for a similar electric race car spaceframe, with minor differences attributable to the varying chassis dimensions. These comparisons confirm that, despite the simplifications inherent in an automated preliminary tool, the generated outputs are consistent with established literature, validating the framework's capability to provide realistic assessments. The *second case study* (autonomous steering system) presents different results. Although the total impact (575.3 kg CO_{2,eq}) and cost (€ 3445) are lower in absolute terms than those of the chassis, the assembly's composition is more critical for resource use. The presence of permanent magnets (PMs) and electronic actuators introduces materials with high supply risk and specific recycling challenges. The tool's ability to identify and quantify these distinct component categories enables designers to visualize trade-offs among mass reduction, functional performance, and environmental impact early in the design phase.

Moving to recyclability considerations, a key contribution of this study is the comparative analysis between the standard automotive recyclability calculation (ISO 22628) and the more conservative, efficiency-based approach (ISO 21106/UNIFE). For the chassis, the difference is minimal (RR drops from 100% to 98%), reflecting the mature industrial infrastructure for ferrous metal recovery. However, the autonomous steering system reveals a finer scenario. The gap between the theoretical ISO 22628 rates and the adjusted ISO 21106 rates (Table 2) highlights the efficiency losses associated with processing composite materials, elastomers, and electronic subcomponents. This difference

is critical for completing realistic Digital Product Passports (DPPs). Relying solely on ISO 22628 can lead to an overestimation of the vehicle's circularity potential. By incorporating process efficiency factors, the proposed framework provides a “reality check” for designers. The calculated end-of-life (EoL) credits, 402.8 kg CO_{2,eq} for the chassis and 32.3 kg CO_{2,eq} for the steering system, demonstrate the quantitative advantage of closed-loop recycling strategies. While these credits may appear modest compared to the total production impact, they represent evident “avoided burdens” essential to achieving carbon-neutrality goals.

From an operational perspective, the substantial reduction in delivery times for technical estimation observed during these case studies suggests that VBA-integrated workflow can support the automotive industry development cycles. The ability to generate a CCBOM complies with the new Formula Student regulations and, most importantly, represents a first step toward the requirements of OEM supply chains subject to the European Green Deal. Data processing, from analyzing SolidWorks assemblies to generating results, is typically completed in just a few minutes using laptops capable of running 3D CAD software (i.e. no HPC systems are necessary). In fact, in the case studies conducted for both scenarios, the final results were obtained in less than 10 minutes using a standard laptop. This has made it possible to drastically reduce analysis time compared to manually compiling Excel spreadsheets and performing various calculations, a process that would take at least several hours, with an estimated time savings of approximately 90-99%.

While the framework provides valuable early-stage feedback, its limitations must be critically acknowledged. First, the current “cradle-to-gate” LCA scope omits the product's use phase. Since the tool aims to support Circular Design, ignoring the energy consumption of active components (such as the autonomous steering system) could lead to suboptimal decision-making. Second, the methodology relies heavily on deterministic input parameters and external LCI databases (e.g., Ecoinvent) without incorporating an automated sensitivity analysis. Consequently, the economic and environmental outputs are highly sensitive to the assumptions embedded in the cost models and database contexts. For instance, the additive manufacturing model assumes a constant infill density rather than a user-defined one, and the welding model simplifies the seam length by using the tube's external diameter instead of the exact laser-profiled intersection. However, as demonstrated by the literature comparison, these geometric simplifications have a negligible impact on the overall estimations and do not compromise the validity of the preliminary results. Therefore, the framework is currently best utilized as a comparative decision-support tool rather than a definitive certification instrument.

Conclusions

This study presented a new computational framework designed to bridge the operational gap between

computer-aided design (CAD) and preliminary sustainability assessment in the automotive industry. By integrating 3D CAD software, such as SolidWorks, with specific scripts, such as using a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet via VBA automation, the developed system successfully automates the extraction of geometric features and the generation of an “extended bill of materials”. This approach responds to industry’s critical need for tools that can translate design data into production and environmental metrics during the early conceptual stages.

The framework is validated through two motorsport case studies, specifically on two assemblies of a Formula Student single-seater car: a tubular chassis and an autonomous steering assembly. The tool demonstrated the practical effectiveness of the methodology. The key results and contributions of this work can be summarized as follows.

- *Workflow efficiency and speed:* The automatic feature recognition logic significantly reduced the delivery times required for technical estimation. By programmatically classifying components (e.g., sheet metal, machined parts, polymers) and assigning process-specific cost models, the framework eliminates the bottleneck of manual data entry, enabling near real-time feedback for complex assemblies, achieving an estimated analysis time savings of 90–99% with final results obtained in less than 10 minutes.
- *Integrated sustainability metrics:* The tool successfully provided simultaneous results for manufacturing costs and carbon footprint (GWP100 in kg CO_{2,eq}). The ability to evaluate these factors simultaneously allows engineers to identify “hot spots” where design changes can yield the greatest environmental benefit without compromising economic viability.
- *Circular design support:* In addition to production impact, the framework demonstrated the ability to calculate recyclability (RR) and recoverability (RRR) rates in accordance with ISO 21106 and ISO 22628.
- *Preparation for regulatory compliance:* By incorporating environmental data directly into CAD metadata and generating structured reports, the framework represent a key step toward automated compilation of digital product passports (DPPs), ensuring traceability requirements are met from the early design stage.

Recommendations

Although the current results are promising, their accuracy remains dependent on the granularity of LCI/LCIA databases and the associated costs. Future work will focus on expanding these databases to include a wider range of manufacturing processes and treatments specific to the automotive sector. Furthermore, future development aims to integrate this standalone framework into broader

Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) environments, potentially including links to more structured industry-related data platforms such as CatenaX [41], thus creating a fully continuous data pipeline for industrial-scale automotive development. Additionally, the methodology behind the framework could be included in more comprehensive tools for calculating product circularity and used to find the right balance between performance and sustainability. To do this, it will be essential to include the product use phase in the analysis, especially for automotive products that actively consume energy, such as autonomous steering, active suspension, or traction motors [42,43]. Furthermore, it will be essential to introduce a more specific study of the end-of-life phase, taking into account disassembly, functional recycling, and the actual circularity of the materials used [44,45]. In addition, sensitivity analysis methods will need to be incorporated into the tool so that the results can be used to compile the final Digital Product Passports.

In conclusion, the presented framework represents progress toward enabling designers to make more informed decisions from the early 3D CAD design stage. Its main industrial application scenarios include the conceptual development of automotive subsystems and the rapid comparative assessment of different design variants to comply with eco-design directives. By facilitating these processes without delaying the development cycle, the framework aligns with the evolving requirements for environmental impact management and anticipated future regulations, such as the compilation of Digital Product Passports, in the automotive industry.

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Nomenclature, Definitions, Acronyms, Abbreviations

GHG - Greenhouse Gas

OEM - Original Equipment Manufacturers

CE - Circular Economy

DPP - Digital Product Passport

IMDS - International Material Data System

LCA - Life Cycle Assessment

CAD - Computer Aided Design

BOM - Bill of Materials

VBA - Visual Basic for Applications
API - Application Programming Interface
KPI - Knowledge-Based Engineering
PLA - Polylactic Acid
ABS - Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
GWP - Global Warming Potential
LCIA - Life Cycle Impact Assessment
EF - Environmental Footprint
ISO - International Standard Organization
EoL - End of Life
RR - Reuse and Recycle
RRR - Reuse, Recycle and Recover

MRF - Material Recovery Facilities
PDF - Portable Document Format
SAE - Society of Automotive Engineers
CCBOM - Costed Carbonized Bill of Material
FRT - Firenze Race Team
PM - Permanent Magnets
CRM - Critical Raw Material
REE - Rare Earth Element
HPC - High Performance Computing
LCI - Life Cycle Inventory
PLM - Product Lifecycle Management

Appendix

TABLE A1 VBA Implementation and Visualization Details

CAD Feature Tree Traversal Logic.

The core of the algorithm resides in the feature tree traversal function, designated as *ProcessComponent*. Assuming that all CAD parts and assemblies have been properly prepared including material and feature attributes, the system employs a recursive approach for model exploration. This facilitates not only the analysis of top-level components but also deep penetration into all nested sub-assemblies. Such an approach ensures that no component, regardless of its depth within the assembly hierarchy or visual occlusion, is omitted from evaluation. The software implements advanced logic to determine the nature of the components, surpassing simple nomenclature verification by interpreting geometric characteristics and metadata. Computational time is reduced through dual-bypass optimization based on the BOM ID. The algorithm skips the computationally heavy 3D geometric extraction for standard commercial (“Buy”) parts, updating only their quantities.

Visual Optimization Algorithm.

To maximize the clarity of the final report, the code integrates a module for automatic screenshot generation. A “visual optimization” algorithm has been implemented, executing the following operations for every individual component:

- *Isolation*. The component is visually isolated from the rest of the assembly.
- *Cleaning*. Work planes, visible sketches, and reference axes that would obfuscate the image are hidden.
- *Standardization*. A predefined isometric view is applied to ensure visual uniformity across the dataset.
- *Centering*. A dual zoom-to-fit command is executed to ensure the object is perfectly centered and occupies the maximum available display area.
- *Import*. The image is finally imported into the target Excel cell, dynamically resized while maintaining the correct aspect ratio.

Additionally, a caching system prevents redundant screenshot generation for already processed components. These bypasses eliminate repetitive tasks, enabling near real-time processing of complex assemblies.

TABLE A2 Cost Analysis formulations

$Cost_{Sheet\ Metal} = (W_{flat} \times C_{mat}) + \left(\frac{P_{cut}}{v_{laser}(T)} \times C_{h_laser} \right) + (N_{bends} \times C_{bend})$	(1)
<p>Where W_{flat} (kg) is the weight of the flat pattern sheet metal, calculated by multiplying the volume of the flattened solid by the specific density ρ of the material; C_{mat} (€/kg) is the unit cost of the raw material extracted from the Raw Materials sheet; P_{cut} (mm) is the total cutting perimeter, including the outer contours and inner slots; $v_{laser}(T)$ (mm/min) is the laser cutting feed rate, obtained by interpolation from the experimental data in the Laser Cut sheet as a function of thickness T; C_{h_laser} (€/min) is the hourly operating cost of the laser cutting machine; N_{bends} is the number of bends identified by analyzing the bend lines in the sketch; C_{bend} (€/bend) is the unit cost per bending operation, which includes setup and handling time.</p>	
$Cost_{Additive} = (m_{part} \times C_{filament}) + (t_{print} \times C_{h_printer})$	(2)
<p>Where m_{part} (g) is the net mass of the printed component; $C_{filament}$ (€/g) is the specific cost of the polymer; t_{print} (h) is the estimated printing time, calculated based on volume and infill factor; $C_{h_printer}$ (€/h) is the hourly machine rate differentiated by technology.</p>	
$Cost_{Machining} = (V_{bbox} \times \rho \times C_{raw}) + (V_{rem} \times C_{removal})$	(3)
<p>Where V_{bbox} (cm³) is the volume of the maximum dimensions parallelepiped, which simulates the starting raw material (bar or block); ρ (g/cm³) is the density of the material; C_{raw} (€/kg) is the cost of the raw material, including the surcharge for standard sizes; V_{rem} (cm³) is the volume of material removed ($V_{bbox} - V_{net}$); $C_{removal}$ (€/cm³) is the specific cost of volumetric removal (MRR Cost), differentiated in the sheet according to the hardness of the material and the strategy.</p>	
$Cost_{Welding} = L_{beads} \times C_{welding}$	(4)
<p>Where L_{beads} (m) is the length of weld beads and $C_{welding}$ (€/m) is the specific cost of the chosen welding operation.</p>	

TABLE A3 Chassis Case Study – Total Results

Chassis / Welding Jigs		
ASSEMBLY NAME:		
1. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS (COST BREAKDOWN)		
Category	Value [€]	Impact %
Raw Materials	€ 6.138,19	79,30%
Commercial Parts	€ 0,00	0,00%
3D Materials	€ 0,00	0,00%
Sheet Metal Process	€ 0,80	0,01%
3D Print Process	€ 0,00	0,00%
Machining Process	€ 1.119,39	14,46%
Welding Process	€ 482,50	6,23%
TOTAL PRODUCTION COST	€ 7.740,87	100,00%
2. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT (LCA - kg CO_{2,eq})		
Category	Value [kg CO _{2,eq}]	Impact %
Raw Materials	1198,81	55,65%
Commercial Parts	0,00	0,00%
3D Materials	0,00	0,00%
Sheet Metal Process	0,11	0,01%
3D Print Process	0,00	0,00%
Machining Process	952,96	44,24%
Welding Process	2,39	0,11%
TOTAL CARBON FOOTPRINT	2154,27	100,00%
3. CIRCULARITY INDICATORS (ISO & EoL)		
ISO 22628 - Recyclability Rate (RR)	100,00%	
ISO 22628 - Recoverability Rate (RRR)	100,00%	
ISO 21106 - Recyclability Rate (RR)	98,00%	
ISO 21106 - Recoverability Rate (RRR)	99,80%	
END OF LIFE CREDIT (Avoided Burden)	402,78 kgCO_{2,eq}	

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TABLE A4 Autonomous Steering Case Study – Total Results

Autonomous Steering		
ASSEMBLY NAME:		
1. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS (COST BREAKDOWN)		
Category	Value [€]	Impact %
Raw Materials	€ 306,95	8,91%
Commercial Parts	€ 3.025,08	87,82%
3D Materials	€ 2,12	0,06%
Sheet Metal Process	€ 0,46	0,01%
3D Print Process	€ 13,76	0,40%
Machining Process	€ 96,25	2,79%
Welding Process	€ 0,00	0,00%
TOTAL PRODUCTION COST	€ 3.444,61	100,00%
2. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT (LCA - kg CO_{2,eq})		
Category	Value [kg CO _{2,eq}]	Impact %
Raw Materials	92,47	16,07%
Commercial Parts	35,36	6,15%
3D Materials	340,22	59,14%
Sheet Metal Process	0,05	0,01%
3D Print Process	6,78	1,18%
Machining Process	100,38	17,45%
Welding Process	0,00	0,00%
TOTAL CARBON FOOTPRINT	575,26	100,00%
3. CIRCULARITY INDICATORS (ISO & EoL)		
ISO 22628 - Recyclability Rate (RR)	98,73%	
ISO 22628 - Recoverability Rate (RRR)	98,73%	
ISO 21106 - Recyclability Rate (RR)	97,29%	
ISO 21106 - Recoverability Rate (RRR)	98,46%	
END OF LIFE CREDIT (Avoided Burden)	32,29 kgCO_{2,eq}	

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